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EFFICIENCY INCREASING MECHANISMS OF BLENDED LEARNING OF STUDENTS IN INSTITUTIONS OF HIGHER PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: analysis and characterization of existing models of blended learning and substantiation of mechanisms for increasing their effectiveness in institutions of higher pedagogical education.

Methodology: The authors used logical, structural and reflective analysis of sources published in international, national and local periodicals; publications placed in scientometric databases; analysis of reports and generalization of the results of the National Agency for Quality Assurance of Higher Education; empirical data obtained as a result of using the Google Trends service to analyze a sample of valid and unfiltered search queries made by users of search engines for research keywords.

Findings: In the conditions of global isolation during pandemic of COVID-19 and development of digital technologies, priorities are given to blended forms of learning. Similar is observed in the conditions of the war in Ukraine: according to the results of statistical data, it is established that more than 40% of the study time in institutions of higher education is provided in the format of blended learning. The main regulatory mechanisms for increasing the effectiveness of students' educational activities during the blended learning are substantiated - metacognitive processes and reflection. Growing interest of scientists in studying metacognition of such constructs as self-regulation, literacy, thinking strategies, motivation, meta-strategies, conceptual understanding, reflection and critical thinking has been revealed.

Originality of the article consists in identifying and substantiating the main regulatory mechanisms for increasing the effectiveness of students' educational activities in the process of blended learning.

Keywords: *blended learning, strategies, models, metacognitive processes, reflection.*

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